

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICABILITY IN FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article covers issues of development of communicability in future English teachers, describes the possibilities of using psychological training in the formation of communicability in students. The article also provides modern methods that can be used for the purpose of forming professional-communicative skills of future English teachers, procedures for conducting psychological training in students that develop communicatively, culture of treatment, form alertness and reflexivity.*

Keywords: *attitude, communicability, reflexivity, empathy, perceptive, teacher's level of communicability, psychological training.*

Introduction

The concept of new education until 2030, adopted by international organizations and developed countries, was described as “the main driving force of Education and development and an important activity that brings it to the goals of Sustainable Development [5]”. It should be noted that in the world, special attention is paid to the issue of assessing the professional skills of teachers at different stages of their professional activity. An example of the early research on this issue in the world is the Holmes Group Project[3], which was introduced at the Faculty of Education at Harvard University. The first stage of this comprehensive study, called “Teachers Of Tomorrow [4]”, was aimed at preparing teachers for professional activities and seeking measures to increase their prestige in society. At the global level, such research is still ongoing. Even today, as one of the important factors in the reform of the educational system, special attention is paid to the preparation of teachers for professional activities, including the integration of interethnic cultural, social, economic, political relations, the training of teachers of foreign languages, in particular English, which are considered the main means of information transmission and communication.

In the following years, public policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is also carried out in the field of education and is aimed at a specific goal, was recognized as one of the priority directions for the development of social society. The president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev noted, “education is the most important and priority issue in which any state and society decides not only today, but also Tomorrow ” [1]. In a time when the role of our state in the world community is growing and cultural and economic ties between countries are strengthening, teaching foreign language to young people who create its future, cultivating speech skills in a foreign language, teaching to communicate is one of the most important urgent problems of the present day. Able to ensure the modern development of Uzbekistan in international templates through in-depth teaching of foreign languages, an independent thinking, knowledgeable specialist pursues the goal of training personnel who have matured in every possible way. To do this, it is necessary to train future English teachers as

specialists who fully meet world standards, develop their professional and communicative skills, fully realize their professional and creative potential.

Materials and studies

The development of professional-communicative competency of the future English teacher as a mature specialist should help the growing youth to find their place in labor activities, receive quality education, qualitatively acquire language skills, develop information competencies, form interpersonal socio-cultural dialogues, but the most important thing in this is the urgent problem of developing the individual to the level of Scientists believe that the ability to build communication with students and their colleagues also occupies a special place in the activities of future English teachers. In this case, it acts as a means of scientific and pedagogical communication between the teacher and students, a condition for improving professional skills, creating a favorable psychological climate in the student audience. To do this, future English teachers must have special professorial-communicative qualifications: knowledge of the personality of the student; organization of student activities in the educational process in the form of cooperation, creative research; perception and correct assessment of the communication situation; sympathy, compassion, understanding of the student's personality; harmony of respect for the student's personality, which is in high demand based on humanistic methods of interaction, etc.k[6]. The professional-communicative competence of future English teachers covers not only the knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for professional activities, the quality of a set of personal qualities, but also the ability to communicate, improve and develop oneself, approach professional activities with creativity and responsibility. Because a teacher should be not only an educated person, an advanced person in his sphere, but also a holder of reflexive, communicative, perceptual qualifications, able to convey to others the knowledge and intellectual reserve that exists at the same time, apply theoretical knowledge in practice without difficulty

Researcher V.V.Davidov [9] believes that “the cognitive component will be related to the level of cognition of another person and involves anticipating the behavior of another person; the emotional component encompasses emotional compassion and present-day empathy, empathy, self-human exposure, empathy, and ability to grieve together, attentiveness to the actions of a partner; the behavioral component primarily covers the acquisition of verbal and nonverbal tools of social behavior”. For successful communication, a person must possess two main areas of communication: external and internal, that is, first a person must learn to understand himself, hear himself, negotiate with himself, control himself, and then - establish contact with other people. Therefore, psychological and communicative trainings are, firstly, psychological, and secondly, technological. Communicative training literally means" common "or"shared use by all". Communication is usually understood as communication, the transfer of information from person to person, a specific form of interaction that people have during their activities. In a practical sense, it is the process of sharing ideas and information that leads to mutual understanding between two or more people[10].

Discussion

The main purpose of psychological and communicative training is to introduce into human activity an effective mechanism for the perception and understanding, coding, transmission and exchange of information. During the training of psychological and communicative training, work is carried out at each stage of these elements.

The entire communication system, complex relations between people, Communication

Management System are implemented.

Students know themselves, its features, strengths and weaknesses, understand the peculiarities of perception, encode information.

In students, the skills of self-presentation and recitation develop.

Develops skills in the effective creation of verbal and non-verbal messages.

The means of conveying information and their properties are studied for the ability of a person to choose suitable means in a given situation.

It develops the reasons for understanding, predicting the behavior of other individuals, and the ability to understand, listen and hear.

The clock develops the skills of feedback.

In the training of psychological and communicative training, participants are taught technologies for the effective performance of all communication functions. Below we will cite examples from communicative trainings that increase communication and speech in future English teachers. One of the most important requirements for the educational system is to teach independent thinking. Today, there are the following communicative-training exercises for future teachers, relying on the experience of educators from the United States and Great Britain [2]:

"Solving a creative problem" - to apply this method, the beginning of the story is read, and students are asked to decide how to end it;

"Quiz Cards" are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, saving time.

"Problem situation solution" (Creative problem solving) to apply this method, the beginning of the story is read How to end readers, referencing;

Quick answers (quick answers) helps to improve the effectiveness of the lesson mentioned;

"Wrote Chigil" (Warm-up exercises) using different games in the audience to interest students in Class" [2];

"Pantomime" (Pantomime) is a method that can be used when a student is tired of doing a lesson or writing exercises that need to explain very difficult topics;

The "story chain" (a chain story) method refers to the oral speech of students helps increase and strengthen memory;

"Role-playing games" (Acting characters) this method can be used in all types of classes. To teach the craft, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the lesson and talk to students;

Thinkers meeting U.Shakespeare, A.Navoi, R.Poets and writers such as Burns can be "invited". The use of the wise words that they uttered at such a time in the lesson will help to educate young people as perfect people;

The **"when pictures speak"** method is much more convenient, when teaching English, it helps in the development of students ' oral speech, for which it is necessary to use pictures on the topic;

"Quiz Cards" are dealt cards based on the number of students and allow all students to participate in the class at the same time-saving time" [2].

Arguments: are held in a manner of mutual exchange of opinions on a topic, dividing study groups into two groups.

Icebreaker: aimed at removing the barrier among educators and learners.

Games: business or role-playing games. Only in this game, instead of text materials, a life situation is staged, which is played by students in a role.

Work with a book: methods aimed at the fact that this method is able to consciously state the content of the given text, self-examination qualifications, independent assimilation of educational materials by educators.

Individial (practical method). Learners focus their knowledge gained in their activities on solving a practical task.

Conversation: these are dialogue, question and answer methods of teaching and reading. The interview can take the form of an individial and a group.

Training others: in this method, learners teach each other information and information on the problem posed.

Round table-trainees sit at the round table and write answers to each other's questions through an envelope. Today, pedagogical activity is difficult to imagine without psychological and communicative methods, since the only goal observed from the study of the basics of any science is to bring a mature specialist to adulthood. In this context, communication is carried out by speakers through different sentences. In such cases, the teacher should not find the opinions of students incorrect, but should, on the contrary, help, encourage students as much as possible, encourage them not to be afraid to say a wrong opinion, and at the end, analyze each of the opinions expressed on his own.

Conclusion

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that the use of psychological training and communicative training in English lessons significantly affects the growth of student communicability. In them, logical thinking skills develop, speech becomes fluent, the skills for a quick and full response are formed. This kind of training and training will increase students' interest in learning a foreign language. Students seek thorough preparation for classes, making students active subjects of the educational process. I am aware of the experiences that when communicative training is used in the course of the lesson, there is an increase in the ability to work in the student body, an easier level of solving conflict situations, an increase in students' stress resistance, an increase in the effectiveness of the communication process, an increase in the quality of preparation for professional activities.

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